

INFORMED CONSENT

I, the undersigned, declare that I, as a participant in a research project in the Department of Translating, Interpreting and Communication, in the MULTIPLES research group under the direction of the Faculty of Arts and Philosophy at Ghent University,

- (1) have been informed about the research objectives, the questions and the tasks that I will encounter during the research and that I was given the opportunity to receive further information if desired;
- (2) will participate out of free will in the research project
- (3) give informed consent to the researchers to store my data confidentially and process and report my data in anonymized form;
- (4) am aware of the option to stop my participation in this research at any moment in time without having to provide a reason;
- (5) know that participating or stopping my participation in the research has no negative consequences of any kind for me;
- (6) am aware of the option to ask the researcher for a summary of the results after the study is finished and the results have been known;
- (7) agree that my data may be used for further analysis by other researchers after complete anonymization;
- (8) am aware that Ghent University is the responsible entity with regards to the personal information collected during the study. I am also aware that the data protection officer can give me more information about the protection of my personal information. Contact: Ms Hanne Elsen (privacy@ugent.be).

Read and approved on the (date),

Signature of the participant

Name of the responsible researcher: Greet De Baets (Ms) available at greet.debaets@ugent.be